

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH BIVALENT METALS.
PART XII. COPPER AND NICKEL PIPERAZINE
DIBIGUANIDE AND THEIR SALTS

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Piperazine dibiguanide, prepared from piperazine and dicyandiamide, has been found to act as a quadridentate group, furnishing four points of attachment to a central metal atom with the formation of metal-biguanide complexes of the inner metallic type. Preparation and properties of cupric piperazine dibiguanide hydroxide, its chloride, sulphate and nitrate, as well as of nickel piperazine dibiguanide hydroxide, its chloride and sulphate, besides of a dinickel piperazine dibiguanide hydroxide, have been described. The constitution of the last named compound has also been discussed.

Piperazine dibiguanide was prepared by condensing piperazine (I) with dicyandiamide. This was found to serve as a quadridentate molecule supplying four points of attachment to a central metal atom like Cu or Ni, giving rise to inner metallic complexes of ethylene dibiguanide type (II).

With nickel salts in strongly alkaline medium a yellow coloured nickel piperazine dibiguanide base was obtained, having the composition, $\text{Ni}_2[\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{N}_2(\text{BigH})_2](\text{OH})_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{N}_2(\text{BigH})_2$ is a molecule of piperazine dibiguanide. The substance gives a paramagnetic moment of $2.48\mu_B$, unlike the other nickel complexes with the same ligand, which are all diamagnetic, a property characteristic of all planar nickel complexes with hybrid dsp^2 bonds. This is best accounted for by the following representation of its configuration as a compound of nickel piperazine dibiguanide hydroxide with nickel hydroxide. It is also supported by the result of dehydration at 110° , when the substance loses five molecules of water.

$\text{Pip}(\text{BigH})_2$ = a molecule of piperazine dibiguanide.

The nickel in nickel piperazine dibiguanide being diamagnetic as usual, while the nickel atom in $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ or in $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_4$, giving a paramagnetic moment ($2.8 \mu_B$ - theor.) characteristic of ionic nickel, the moment value for the complex compound as a whole should be equal to that of the latter. This is more or less in agreement with the observed value of $2.48 \mu_B$.

EXPERIMENTAL

Piperazine Dibiguanide Sulphate.—Piperazine (4.3 g.) and dicyandiamide (8.4 g.) were heated with about 75 c.c. of water in a conical flask on the water-bath for about 3 hours with occasional additions of 5 c.c. of copper sulphate solution (10 g. in 30 c.c. water) at intervals of 20 minutes. To the resulting mixture, a solution of NaOH (2.8 g.) was added, and the heating was continued till the mixture turned red. This was cooled and filtered; and the red residue was then decomposed with sulphuric acid (1:3), when the white piperazine dibiguanide sulphate separated out gradually on cooling. This was filtered and washed with cold water until free from copper. The product was then dissolved in ammonia and a little NaOH, the mixture filtered and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid (1:1). On cooling, shining white crystals of piperazine dibiguanide sulphate separated out from the solution. These were filtered, washed with cold water and dried in air. (Found: N, 29.40; S, 13.37. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_{10} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 29.35; S, 13.41 per cent).

Copper Piperazine-dibiguanide Hydroxide.—Piperazine dibiguanide sulphate (4.7 g.), dissolved in ammonia and a little caustic soda solution (about 20 c.c. of 2N-NaOH), was treated with an ammoniacal solution of copper sulphate (1.6 g.) with constant stirring. The precipitate of red-violet copper piperazine dibiguanide hydroxide, which separated immediately, was filtered and washed with cold water till free from sulphate. The product was dried in a desiccator to a constant weight. {Found: Cu, 15.46; N, 34.80; H_2O (by loss at 105°), 21.97. $[\text{Cu.Pip}(\text{BigH})_2](\text{OH})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 15.60; N, 34.50; H_2O , 22.10 per cent}. [Found (anhydrous compound): Cu, 20.07; N, 44.31. Calc. Cu, 20.10; N, 44.30 per cent].

The substance forms red-violet powder, insoluble in water and alcohol. When heated with solutions of ammonium salts, it liberates ammonia. It is readily decomposed by dilute acids.

Copper piperazine-dibiguanide chloride was obtained as a red-violet residue when the complex copper base was heated with a solution of ammonium chloride on the water-bath until the evolution of ammonia ceased. The product was filtered, washed with cold water and dried in air. The substance is sparingly soluble in hot water and practically insoluble in alcohol. {Found: Cu, 13.69; Cl, 15.42; H_2O (by loss at 105°), 15.55. $[\text{Cu.Pip}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 13.70; Cl, 15.40; H_2O , 15.60 per cent}. [Found (anhydrous compound): Cu, 16.39; Cl, 18.28. Calc. Cu, 16.34; Cl, 18.27 per cent].

The *complex sulphate* was obtained as a violet compound from the complex base and ammonium sulphate solution in the same way as the complex chloride. The substance is insoluble in water and alcohol. {Found: Cu, 12.57; S, 6.15; H_2O (by loss

at 105°), 19.29. $[\text{Cu.Pip}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 5.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 12.40; S, 6.20; H_2O , 19.31 per cent}. The anhydrous sulphate gives Cu, 15.40; S, 7.72. Calc. Cu, 15.30; S, 7.73 per cent.

The *complex nitrate* was prepared from the complex base and a solution of ammonium nitrate, as described in the previous cases. The substance forms red powder, insoluble in water and alcohol.

{Found: Cu, 13.70; H_2O (by loss at 100°), 3.88. $[\text{Cu.Pip}(\text{BigH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 13.80; H_2O , 3.90 per cent}. [Found (anhydrous compound): Cu, 14.39. Calc. Cu, 14.39 per cent].

Nickel piperazine-dibiguanide nickel hydroxide was obtained as a buff coloured precipitate by adding an ammoniacal solution of nickel sulphate to that of piperazine dibiguanide sulphate in presence of an excess of caustic soda. The product was filtered, washed well with cold water and dried in a desiccator to a constant weight, when the colour of the substance changed to yellow. The substance is insoluble in water and alcohol, and liberates ammonia from ammonium salt solution. {Found: Ni, 21.93; N, 26.40; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 16.80. $[\text{Ni.Pip}(\text{BigH})_2](\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 22.17; N, 26.40; H_2O , 17.00 per cent}. [Found (anhydrous compound): Ni, 26.52; N, 31.85. Calc. Ni, 26.70; N, 31.80 per cent].

Nickel piperazine-dibiguanide chloride was obtained as an insoluble orange-yellow product by heating the complex nickel base, described above, with a solution of ammonium chloride on the water-bath until the evolution of ammonia ceased. The product was washed with cold water and dried in air to a constant weight. {Found: Ni, 11.34; N, 27.22; Cl, 13.48; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 25.88. $[\text{Ni.Pip}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 7.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 11.31; N, 27.00; Cl, 13.60; H_2O , 26.00 per cent}. [Found (anhydrous compound): Ni, 15.19; Cl, 18.49. Calc. Ni, 15.20; Cl, 18.50 per cent].

Nickel piperazine-dibiguanide hydroxide base was obtained as an insoluble orange coloured product by keeping the complex nickel chloride (1 mol.) in contact with a solution of caustic soda (2 mol.) for two days and then heating the mixture on the water-bath for some time. The product was washed with cold water and dried in a desiccator to a constant weight. {Found: Ni, 15.56; N, 37.33; H_2O (by loss at 105°), 16.70. $[\text{Ni.Pip}(\text{BigH})_2](\text{OH})_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 15.70; N, 37.46; H_2O , 16.80 per cent}. Found (anhydrous compound): Ni, 18.88; N, 44.77. Calc. Ni, 18.90; N, 45.05 per cent].

Nickel piperazine-dibiguanide sulphate was prepared by adding an ammoniacal solution of nickel sulphate (1 mol.) to a slightly ammoniacal solution of piperazine dibiguanide sulphate (1 mol.) and then heating the mixture on the water-bath until the solution was practically free from ammonia. The insoluble orange coloured product was filtered, washed with cold water and then dried in air to a constant weight. It can also be obtained by heating the complex nickel base with a solution of ammonium sulphate. {Found: Ni, 12.05; N, 28.46; S, 6.68; H_2O (by loss at 105°), 16.40. $[\text{Ni.Pip}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 4.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 11.90; N, 28.50; S, 6.51; H_2O , 16.54 per cent}. [Found (anhydrous compound): Ni, 14.34; N, 34.31. Calc. Ni, 14.36; N, 34.20 per cent].

Magnetic Susceptibilities.—The magnetic susceptibilities of some of the compounds described above, were measured in a Gouy's balance, and the results are given below.

Substance	χ_g .	χ_g (obs.)	δ (diamagnetic correction)	χ_m (corr.)	μ_n
1. $\text{Cu.Pip}(\text{BigH})_2\text{Cl}_2, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2.61×10^{-4}	1204×10^{-4}	222×10^{-4}	1426×10^{-4}	1.87
2. $[\text{Ni.Pip}(\text{BigH})_2][\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_4], 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	4.31 "	2284 "	217 "	2501 "	2.48
3. $[\text{Ni.Pip}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2, 7.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Diamagnetic.				

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